

ISic1189

I.Sicily inscription 1189

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific

Material

breccia

Object

base

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Haluntium

Place of origin (modern)

San Marco d'Alunzio

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico Regionale Antonino Salinas,
inventory 8815

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. ὁ δᾶμος

2. [B]ίωτον Τιμάνδρο[υ]

3. εὐνοίας ἔνεκεν

Apparatus

Text checked against photograph

Translation (en)

The people (honours) Biotos son of Timander, for the sake of goodwill

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492795

EDCS 39101553

PHI 140673

PHI 175638

Bibliography

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic1189. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4351751>

Photo J. Prag, courtesy Museo Archeologico Regionale Antonino Salinas